

Synthesis of 2-Imino-1',3',4'-triazolyl-3-alkyl/aryl-4-thiazolidones

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In continuation of our previous work¹, synthesis of several new thiazolidones containing the triazolyl moiety have been synthesised and their constitutions confirmed by degradation to the known products.

4-Amino-1,2,4-triazole² was condensed with various isothiocyanates in ethanol in order to obtain the corresponding thioureas. These on being condensed with chloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate afforded the title compounds. Acid hydrolysis of these thiazolidones yielded the known 3-arylthiazolin-2,4-diones, thus confirming the constitution assigned to them.

N-Phenyl-N'-1',3',4'-Triazolyl-thiourea.—Equimolar amounts of 4-amino-1,2,4-triazole and phenyl isothiocyanate were refluxed in ethanol for about an hour. After filtration, the product was washed with HCl (very dil.) and water and air-dried. Recrystallisation from dilute ethanol afforded colorless crystals, m.p. 105°, yield 58-65%. Thioureas prepared are described in Table I.

TABLE I

N-Alkyl/aryl-*N'*-(1',3',4'-triazolyl)-thioureas (I).

2-Imino-(1',3',4'-(triazolyl))-3-alkyl/aryl-thiazolidin-4-ones (II).

R.	**M.P. (I).	% Sulphur.		**M.P. (II)	% Sulphur.	
		Found.	Reqd.		Found	Reqd.
Ph	105°	14.6	14.6	265°	12.3	12.4
<i>m</i> -Tol	175°	14.3	14.4	110°	12.0	12.1
<i>o</i> -Tol	180°	14.4	14.4	210°	11.9	12.2
<i>p</i> -Tol	188-90°	14.1	14.4	168-70°	12.1	12.2
<i>p</i> -Chloro- Ph	175-76°	12.3	12.6	90°	10.6	10.9
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	179°	13.2	13.4	212°	11.2	11.5
<i>m</i> -Amyl	145-46°	15.0	15.0	190°	12.4	12.6
<i>n</i> -Bu	130°	15.8	16.1	55-57°	13.1	13.4
<i>n</i> -Hexyl	105°	13.8	14.1	84-85°	11.7	11.9
Me	107°	20.0	20.3	*88-90°	16.0	16.2
Et	108°	18.5	18.6	*110°	14.8	15.1
Cyclohexyl	65-66°	13.9	14.2	*68°	12.3	12.1

* Mixed m. p. with the starting product depressed considerably.

** Uncorrected.

1. *This Journal*, 1964, **41**, 704.

2. Herbst and Garrison, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, **18**, 874.

2-Imino-1',3',4'-triazolyl-3-phenylthiazolidin-4-one.—To a solution of *N*-phenyl-*N'*-1',3',4'-triazolyl-thiourea (1.1 g., 0.005*M* in 25 ml of anhydrous ethanol) were added chloroacetic acid (0.52 g., 0.0055*M*) and fused sodium acetate (0.62g., 0.007*M*). The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was treated with cold water and kept overnight. The insoluble product obtained was dried and recrystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 265°. All thiazolidones described were prepared by this general method. The average yield of thiazolidones was found to be 48 to 55%.

Hydrolysis of 2-Imino-1',3',4'-triazolyl-3-phenylthiazolidin-4-one.—A mixture of the title product (1 g.), ethanol (20 ml), and HCl (5 ml) was refluxed on a sand bath for about 4 hr. On cooling, the insoluble matter separating was washed with water, dried, and crystallised from ethanol; m.p. 146°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 3-phenylthiazolidin-2,4-dione³ remained undepressed. The filtrate after neutralisation and ether extraction yielded traces of 4-amino-1, 2, 4-triazole.

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